

ZERO COST POST ELECTION MANUAL RECOUNT

Requirements: Two Volunteers with Facebook Account

Any Filipino can volunteer under Volunteer Act of 2007

Rules and Process for Manual Counting:

1. Only 10% Barangays of a City can be manually counted for simplicity. Like sampling in statistics.
2. The name of Barangays in a City shall be put in a transparent box. Randomly pick 10% of Barangays or two Barangays whichever is higher. Example in a City with 20 Barangays, 10% of 20 is 2 Barangays.

All machines with voters receipts in the 2 Barangays shall undergo manual counting.

3. Two volunteers with a Facebook Account.

The first volunteer using his Facebook Account shall take a recorded Facebook Live video of the second volunteer while doing the scanning of all voters receipts. For transparency purposes.

The second volunteer using his Facebook Account shall manually scan continuously all voters receipt using Facebook Live.

If there are 2000 voters in one Barangay, and it might take 5 seconds to scan each voter receipts.

$2000 \text{ voters receipt} \times 5 \text{ seconds} = 10,000 \text{ seconds}$

$10,000 \text{ seconds} = 2 \text{ hours, } 46 \text{ minutes and } 40 \text{ seconds.}$

If there are two Barangays, the whole scanning can only be done in less than approx 5 hours.

4. The name of two volunteers shall be registered with COMELEC.

Ideally, the random selection and scanning of the Barangays shall be done in the same day.

All ballot boxes in a city shall be in one storage building only. So the volunteers can easily get them for scanning at the start of the manual scanning.

5. The public or netizens can count the result of 10% or two Barangays in their free time. Just watch the Facebook Live of the scanned individual votes. Anyone can also audit the counting since it's Facebook Live.

6. Compare the results to the election outcome in the COMELEC website. As COMELEC posted the result per Barangay level.

7. If there is at least 10% discrepancy, or any percentage discrepancy that can change the outcome of the local election. Proceed with manual scanning of all voters receipt of all Barangays in that City.

8. There shall be failure of the election if the result of manual counting is different to the COMELEC result posted online.

9. The above process can be done in all cities of the Philippines at zero cost with just two volunteers using their Facebook Live Account.

Note: Because of Privacy Law, the volunteer must fold the upper part of the voter receipt to scan only the candidates part.

To determine whether the voter receipt is the same as the ballot paper (or paper shaded by voters), scan all ballot papers right after scanning the voter receipt.

Possible issue: "Your vote is sacred, no one must know it."

Solution: Just fold the upper part of the voter receipt or ballot paper before scanning. So the volunteer will only scan the name of the candidates.

The goal is to ensure the integrity of the election - at zero cost, compared to the lengthy process and ridiculous fees if a local candidate files a petition for manual counting.

Domino Effect: If there is at least one city with a huge discrepancy from manual recount and automated results, the candidates of other cities might follow. The public will eventually figure out the problem behind 17 Million overvoting.

Every election, there are people who want to do a manual recount. Even in 2019, Ferdinand 'Bongbong' Marcos Jr. requested a manual recount against Leni Robredo for certain provinces and cities. He could afford it, so a manual recount was conducted.

I understand that NAMFREL and PPCRV are already part of the random manual counting. However, it's not clear how the precincts were randomly chosen. I read news reports that the process was conducted behind closed doors, with limited media access, and involved the use of a website. The selection of precincts for random manual counting should be open, public, and transparent.